

Robust Coil Combination for Low-SNR X-Nuclear MRSI

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DEUTERIUM METABOLIC IMAGING PHOSPHOROUS MAGNETIC RESONANCE SPECTROSCOPY X-NUCLEAR COIL COMBINATION

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Impact

In order to move X-nuclear MR into clinical routine, robust methods dealing with limited SNR are required. Multi-channel receive coils can improve spatial coverage and SNR, but require robust and fully-automatic coil combination methods for reproducible, high-SNR results.

Synopsis

Motivation: Coil combination is challenging in X-nuclear MRSI with low SNR, especially for coils with many receive channels resonating at lower frequencies.

Goals: Goal is to improve the quality and robustness of coil combination in MRSI of different X-nuclei, namely ²H, ³¹P and ¹²⁹Xe.

Approach: Two different coil combination methods based on Singular-Value Decomposition (SVD) and Linear-Least Squares (LSQ) were implemented and combined with improvements (noise decorrelation and polynomial smoothing). SNR was compared for various coils in different in vivo applications.

Results: SNR of pseudo images was improved by a factor of 1.4 up to >7 for different coils and nuclei.

Introduction

MR Spectroscopic Imaging (MRSI) of X-nuclei such as ²H and ³¹P is SNR limited, hence requiring long acquisition durations for averaging and restricting achievable resolutions. Multi-channel receive coils can improve spatial coverage and SNR, especially near the coil elements, but require the combination of data from individual coil elements during reconstruction. MRSI data is reconstructed spatially and then combined voxel-by-voxel through phasing and weighting of the individual coil elements followed by summation over this dimension. Individual phases and weights in space are equivalent to receive coil sensitivities maps.

While most methods work equally well for high-SNR data, obtaining sufficiently good sensitivity maps gets challenging for low SNR of individual coil elements. Goal of this work was to improve robustness of coil combination of MRSI data by implementing and comparing two methods - Singular-Value Decomposition (SVD) [1] and Linear-Least Squares (LSQ) [2] - and combine them with noise decorrelation [1] and polynomial smoothing [3].

Methods

After Gaussian apodisation in spectral domain (5Hz), data was reconstructed spatially and the following steps were performed in time domain of spectral dimension:

Noise decorrelation (NDC): Noise was extracted from 15% of lowest signal of actual data and used to calculate the noise covariance, which in turn was used to decorrelate the data of individual coil elements according to [1,4].

Sensitivity maps were determined via the **SVD** method described in [1] in combination with phasing all coil elements via first FID points; or the **LSQ** (=L2-Optimal) method described in [2], which directly yields correctly phased spectra.

Polynomial smoothing (PS): Sensitivity maps were smoothed spatially via polynomial interpolation [3].

Coil combination: Individual voxels were phase-corrected and weighted using the complex, RMS-normalised coil sensitivities before summing the data over the coil dimension [5]. Final reconstruction step is to Fourier transform the data in spectral dimension.

SNR maps were calculated in spectral domain by calculating the root-of-sum-of-squares signal in a 600Hz around peak maximum and dividing it through the (complex) standard-deviation of 30% of data at the spectral edge (=noise). SNR improvements were then calculated by dividing those SNR maps through the reference SNR map (SVD without NDC and PS).

Experimental: Density-weighted MRSI [6] was acquired on different 3T/7T MRI scanners (Premier+MR750+Signa7T, GE HealthCare) equipped with X-nuclear capabilities using different ²H, ³¹P and ¹²⁹Xe coils in healthy volunteers (details in [Fig. 1](#)).

Results and Discussion

3-plane pseudo images extracted from 4 largest spectral points are shown in [Fig. 2](#) for coil combinations using pure SVD and LSQ+NDC, respectively. SNR enhancements relative to pure SVD were calculated over a region with signal comparing the different methods in [Fig. 1](#). Spectra in the centre of the FOV are shown in [Fig. 3](#) and noise covariance matrices in [Fig. 4](#).

Noise decorrelation (NDC) consistently improves SNR even for well-decoupled coils. Polynomial smoothing seems to have limited advantage when data is noise decorrelated. The ^2H abdominal data generally had much lower SNR with SVD coil combination basically breaking down. Here, using LSQ and NDC significantly increased SNR.

Another advantage of LSQ is its simpler implementation and its inherently correct spectral phasing. Phase in SVD is arbitrary, and often either normalised to first coil element or by phasing the spectra afterwards. Both SVD and LSQ were already optimised for low-SNR data by truncating data to 64 largest signal points. Methods getting the complex weight only from first point of FID or highest spectral peak were not considered due to lack of robustness for noisy data.

Conclusions

The same combination works robustly for all data enabling an automatic data reconstruction of various types of nuclei, applications and setups. LSQ+NDC can considerably enhance SNR in case of low SNR sensitivity maps, as demonstrated here with ^2H natural abundance abdominal signal.

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Figures and Tables

Nucleus	f0	#Rx	Vendor	ROI	SVD+PS	SVD+NDC	SVD+NDC+PS	LSQ	LSQ+PS	LSQ+NDC	LSQ+NDC+PS
2H	19.6	16	Magtron	brain	1.024±0.04	1.62±0.13	1.65±0.13	1.43±0.07	1.45±0.08	1.72±0.14	1.72±0.14
2H	19.6	16	Magtron	abdomen	1.75±1.07	6.20±3.13	6.25±3.15	3.47±1.67	3.56±1.72	7.24±3.58	7.24±3.60
2H	19.6	32	Magtron	abdomen	1.08±0.16	4.01±1.06	4.12±1.10	2.12±0.56	2.17±0.58	4.39±1.17	4.38±1.17
31P	51.7	8	Rapid	brain	0.98±0.03	1.44±0.06	1.44±0.07	1.25±0.05	1.27±0.05	1.46±0.08	1.47±0.07
129Xe	35.3	8	JD Coils	lungs	1.06±0.19	1.10±0.12	1.19±0.26	1.38±0.60	1.40±0.66	1.40±0.67	1.43±0.72
31P@7T	120.6	32	TDC	legs	1.02±0.12	2.18±0.51	2.21±0.53	1.45±0.27	1.47±0.29	2.43±0.59	2.44±0.59

Scan for high-resolution version

Figure 1: SNR improvements relative to pure SVD-based coil combination for SVD and LSQ methods combined with Noise Decorrelation (NDC) and polynomial smoothing (PS) for different coils in vivo.

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Figure 2: 3-plane pseudo images with SVD, LSQ and LSQ+NDC coil combination.

Scan for high-resolution version

Figure 3: 3D Representative spectra in the centre of the FOV for SVD (blue line) and LSQ+NDC (red dotted line) coil combination.

Scan for high-resolution version

Figure 4: Noise covariance matrices of used the coils extracted from the noise of the data.